

Report on carbon storage within and beyond biogenic habitats

Deliverable 4.3

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 4.3 overview

This report identifies key variables which regulate organic carbon (OC) levels and storage within and beyond biogenic habitats. Based on the sediment OC data compiled in **Deliverable 4.1** (*Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats*, Graversen et al. 2023b) and **Deliverable 4.2** (*Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats*, Graversen et al. 2023a), we extracted matching environmental data (e.g., current velocity and exposure, distance from shore) and modelled potential drivers of sediment OC content in European seas. We also identified how OC content varied across substrate- and habitat classes. As described in Deliverable 4.1 and Deliverable 4.2, we grouped biogenic and non-biogenic substrates and habitats according to the EUNIS definition. In addition, we used a broader definition of marine vegetated biogenic habitats, including saltmarsh, seagrass, and mixed seagrass/seaweed habitats. We did so because these habitats are known to support biodiversity and are also so-called “blue carbon habitats”, which can accumulate OC in their sediments and potentially can be managed to increase this capacity (Howard et al. 2023).

Our results demonstrate that the main environmental predictors of sediment OC levels were wave exposure, maximum temperature, distance from shore and bathymetry (water depth, hereafter). The highest OC contents were generally found in salt marshes, seagrass meadows (in particular meadows of *Posidonia oceanica*) and in fine mud and coarse and mixed sediment substrata.

These findings lay the foundation for developing a blue carbon scoring system and related blue carbon maps in subsequent tasks. The scoring system will allow us to classify the “blue carbon” levels of different sea basins based on a combination of environmental drivers and habitat characteristics. The blue carbon maps will, together with the biodiversity maps (WP3 - Species and biogenic habitat distributions), serve as a basis for proposing a network of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) that maximises marine biodiversity and carbon stocks across European seas as part of a systematic conservation planning approach.

Background

Ocean sediments represent the world's greatest non-fossil pool of organic carbon (OC) which can be stored for thousands to millions of years (Estes et al. 2019). Overall, levels of OC in marine sediments vary from < 0.1% to > 30%, with the content depending on the geomorphology, physical, chemical and biological conditions (Burdige 2007a). Sediment OC is derived from either marine or terrestrial sources, with the proportion of terrestrial-derived material generally decreasing with distance from shore (Burdige 2007b). In open ocean systems, around 25% of the OC exported from the sunlit layer reaches the seafloor (Dunne et al. 2007) and of this less than 1% is buried and stored in sediments over long timescales (> thousands of years; LaRowe et al. 2020). Coastal and shelf sediments (<1000 m water depth) generally have higher sedimentation rates and burial efficiency resulting in around 3 times higher per area OC standing stocks than in the seafloor of the deeper sea (Atwood et al. 2020; Burdige 2007b).

Multiple studies have demonstrated that some of the sediment OC pools have short turnover times, and are, therefore, quickly depleted (e.g. Cowie & Hedges 1994; Lee et al. 2000). Generally, it is assumed that the reactivity of the sediment OC pool decreases with water depth as well as with depth and age of the sediment (e.g. Parkes et al. 1994; Wellsbury et al. 1997). However, the factors controlling the cycling and storage of OC in sediments are highly complex and are influenced by multiple factors, such as sediment fauna activity, flora and microbes, seabed lithology and granulometry, as well as the chemistry, hydrology and biology of the surrounding water column (e.g. Burdige 2007b; Keil 2017; Mayer 1994). Due to this complexity, OC degradation and storage is highly variable even over smaller scales (e.g. Blair & Aller 2012) and, consequently, disentangling the interplay between controlling factors over time and space is challenging.

The capacity of marine sediments to store OC has recently been embedded in the concept of “blue carbon”, defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as “*all biologically-driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management*”. Blue carbon research has mainly focused on the management of vegetated coastal habitats to protect and increase their capacity to capture carbon dioxide and retain OC while also supporting biodiversity and other key ecological functions (Duarte et al. 2013; Howard et al. 2014; Nellemann & Corcoran 2009). The challenges and opportunities of such “blue carbon” strategies were recently summarised (Gattuso et al. 2023). The blue carbon concept is expanding, and marine sediments are categorised as “emerging blue carbon ecosystems” where human action may be able to increase these sinks (Howard et al. 2023). In addition to further studies on how protection may affect marine sediment OC levels, there is a need for a robust understanding of the factors controlling these. However, despite decades of research into the factors controlling OC storage, relatively few larger scale studies have attempted to link OC levels across diverse seafloor habitats with variables regulating these standing stocks.

Aim and approach

In this report we combine empirical data on sediment OC levels presented in Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023b) and Deliverable 4.2 (Graversen et al. 2023a) with information on environmental conditions and habitat types to identify key factors controlling sediment OC levels within European seas. The findings will also lay the foundation for creating a scoring system which will allow us to determine the relative “blue carbon” level of different areas and sea basins based on environmental conditions (e.g., water temperature, sheltered or wave exposed), substratum (e.g. sandy versus muddy substrata), and other habitat characteristics (e.g., seagrass meadows).

Methods

Data included

For the analysis and modelling we utilise data sourced from the datasets described in Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023b) and Deliverable 4.2 (Graversen et al. 2023a). The dataset consists of directly determined sediment percent total organic carbon (%OC) values and, where available, ancillary data for temperature, water depth, dry bulk density and others as listed in Deliverable 4.1. Specific information was required for inclusion in the database (latitude, longitude, date of sampling, sediment depth intervals and method for sediment retrieval) with further details and a full list of ancillary data provided in Deliverable 4.1. The complete dataset comprises more than ~25,000 data points, consisting of directly measured OC values.

Blue Carbon data

The majority of OC data in the database represented OC as a percentage of dry matter (%OC). Averaging these OC values from the top 10 cm of the sediment resulted in ~6,000 unique data points. This dataset forms the key OC (“blue carbon”) data used in this analysis. This dataset contained 840 paired %OC and dry bulk density (DBD, $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) estimates, with both of these variables needed for calculating sediment OC stocks, which were calculated for the top 10 cm sediment layer by multiplying the weighted average %OC from each datapoint by its weighted average DBD. These OC stocks were calculated and related to OC-levels (%OC) in order to evaluate if the relationships we identified for %OC are also likely to be applicable for OC stocks. It should here be noted that around 53 DBD data points included in Deliverable 4.1 (See Figure 2A in Graversen et al. 2023b) were excluded from this analysis as the results provided by one data provider were erroneous. In addition, as the database contains very few (86) observations of OC accumulation rates, we did not attempt to include these in analyses of large-scale patterns.

EUNIS substrata and habitats

The OC database was supplemented with information about the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) substrata and habitat, classified according to the substrata defined at levels 2-4 of the EUNIS v2019 classification system (Lillis et al. 2021). The source of the substrata data was the predicted habitat model called EUSeaMap 2023 (Vasquez et al. 2023). The data points were plotted in ArcMap 10.1 and spatial joining was used to extract substratum for each individual point. The data sources and classification of the substrata are described in more detail in Appendix 1.

For a broader definition, which includes marine “vegetated biogenic habitats” growing on sedimentary seafloor (all seagrass habitats and saltmarsh habitats, Deliverable 4.1, Graversen et al. 2023b), data contributors also provided additional information on seagrass species. When “NA” was expressed in this category, it was either because the datapoint only contained information about unvegetated sediment or because no information was available.

Wave exposure model and environmental drivers

Wave exposure for coastal areas < 5 km from the shoreline for Europe and the Arctic was calculated using 100-m resolution land mass datasets (Deliverable D2.2, Burrows et al. 2023). Offshore wave exposure was derived using a 5-km resolution land mass dataset projected using UTM30N for European and Atlantic waters and a WGS 84 / Arctic Polar Stereographic projection for the Arctic. Land cells were identified and not included in the analysis. We began by setting the minimum distance to land in each of the sectors to the maximum wave fetch. For every cell in the search, the distance and angular direction from the focal coastal cell were calculated. If the cell was a land cell and the distance to that cell was less than the minimum recorded for that particular sector, then the minimum distance for the sector was set to the new distance value. Wave exposure indices were calculated at a fine scale (50-100 m, 1-2 arcseconds) by modelling wave fetch (the distance to the

nearest land in all directions) around focal grid cells determined using a modified version of the model presented in Burrows et al. (2008) and Burrows (2012). The model involved searches for the nearest land around each cell over gridded search domains up to a maximum of 200 km. Wave fetch was then expressed as the summed distance to the nearest land around each point.

The machine learning eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm was used to model sediment %OC data for European seas against a set of biologically relevant predictor variables. This is a highly effective algorithm, renowned for its high performance, scalability, and regularisation capabilities, which effectively prevent overfitting (de Gouveia et al. 2024; Lamichhane et al. 2019). The OC records were averaged whenever falling on the same cell (see below, Bio-ORACLE resolution of 0.05°, approximately 5 km). This retrieved 4699 unique sites with %OC ranging between 0 and 20%. To improve model fitting, the target variable, "%OC", was log-transformed.

Ten biologically relevant predictor variables were extracted from Bio-ORACLE v3.0 (Assis et al. 2023a), namely, water depth, diffuse attenuation, nitrate, maximum temperature, minimum temperature, phosphate, photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), salinity, current speed and slope. Before modelling, Pearson's correlation coefficient was estimated between all pairs of predictors.

The XGBoost algorithm fitted %OC against the predictor variables using a Gaussian distribution. Hyperparameter tuning, a crucial step in machine learning, was performed with the "grid search" method under a cross-validation framework (Assis et al. 2022; de Gouveia et al. 2024; Ramos Martins et al. 2021). This tested all combinations of the hyperparameters of shrinkage ranging between 0 and 0.5 (step 0.1), gamma between 0 and 5 (step 1), depth between 1 and 3 (step 1), and round between 10 and 100 (step 20), with 20% of data withheld in 3 independent random folds. To mitigate the risk of overfitting, the model incorporated monotonicity constraints, aligning with the anticipated effects of each predictor variable on the %OC response (de Gouveia et al. 2024; Liu et al. 2023). This approach utilised positive constraints for PAR, minimum temperature, salinity and nutrients, and negative for maximum temperature, water speed and slope. Model performance was estimated by cross-validation with deviance explained. The best set of hyperparameters was chosen as the one maximising deviance explained, on average. The significance of the model was explored by determining the relative contribution of each predictor in explaining data variability and by developing partial dependency functions depicting the effect of each predictor on modelled %OC (Elith et al. 2008).

Results

Blue Carbon: In our dataset, dry bulk density (DBD in g cm^{-3}) declined exponentially with increasing %OC (Figure 1A). The fitted relationship tended to overestimate DBD for large values of %OC (Figure 1A), and the parallel plot of DBD vs. $\text{Log}(\%OC)$ showed a large variation around the linear regression line (Figure 1B).

The OC stocks showed an overall positive correlation with %OC in the top 10 cm of the sediment (Figure 2A), however with larger variability at higher %OC. Overall, the deviation from the regression line in the log-log plot (Figure 2B) was divided into two clusters, one with high and one with low OC content (Figure 2B). The marine sediment stores on average 0.89 kg OC per m^2 in the upper 10 cm (interquartile range, IQR: 1.22-0.25) with a max storage of 8.75 kg OC per m^2 .

Figure 1. (A) Relationship between the averaged dry bulk density (DBD in g cm^{-3}) and % organic carbon (%OC) in the top 10 cm of the sediment, fitted with an exponential function. (B) Averaged DBD as a function of the logarithm of averaged %OC in the top 10 cm fitted with a linear model.

Figure 2. Relationship between (A) The averaged organic carbon stock (OCstock, Kg C m^{-2}) and %OC in the top 10 cm of the sediment, and (B) the averaged OC stock as a function of the logarithm of averaged %OC in the top 10 cm of the sediment.

Organic carbon across EUNIS substrata and habitats

The %OC content varied markedly within and between the EUNIS substrata classes. The highest median levels were in “*Limaria hians* beds” (only three observations), “*Posidonia oceanica* meadows”, “Fine mud”, “Fine mud or Sandy mud or Muddy sand”, and “Coarse & mixed sediment”. The lowest %OC occurred in the sediment associated with “*Serpula vermicularis* reefs” (only two observations), “Sand” and “Coarse substrate” (Figure 3A). In terms of EUNIS habitats and marine regions and zones, the highest %OC were recorded in “Biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*” in the Mediterranean Sea, “Bivalve reefs” in the Atlantic”, “Baltic mud” and “Baltic sand or mud” (Figure 3B). Lagoon, offshore circalittoral, circalittoral, and infralittoral were the marine depth zones with highest %OC (Figure 3C). It is important to point out that the grey box plots correspond to Mediterranean *Biocenosis of Posidonia oceanica* (e) and *Biocenosis of muddy detritic bottoms* (h) (Figure 3C).

A comparison of %OC levels across marine vegetated habitats (including EUNIS-defined *Posidonia* habitats, as well as other seagrass habitats and saltmarsh habitats), and other biogenic habitats also showed large variability within each group but with highest median %OC levels in seagrass and saltmarsh habitats (Figure 3D). Among the four European seagrass species, sediments of *Posidonia oceanica* and *Zostera marina* were those with the highest median OC levels while sediments of *Cymodocea nodosa* and *Nanozostera noltei* had lower median levels (Figure 3E).

A total of 394 entries were specified as “Rock and other hard substrata” under EUSeaMap substrata (which is classified according to the EUNIS classification v2019). Since EUSeaMap is a map with a coarse spatial scale, “Rock and other hard substrata” was replaced with not available (NA; Figure 3A, 3B-C, 4A). However, we decided to not subsequently exclude NA from the plots since it indicates potential mismatch between modelled and in-situ observation that need to be harmonised in the final version of the dataset.

For marine vegetated habitats, the variability between their OC stocks showed the same overall pattern as the variability between their OC content (Figure 4).

C)

D)

Figure 3. Boxplots showing weighted averages of %OC for the top 10 cm sediment in different (A) EUNIS substrata, (B-C) EUSeaMap seabed substrata based on EUNIS classification v2019 of habitats at level 3 according to marine regions and zones, respectively, (D) marine vegetated habitats (broader definition, see Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023b)), and (E) seagrass species. Number of observations is indicated at the bottom of each box. In Figure 3B-C, NA indicates non-reported marine region and zone, respectively. The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 25-75 percentiles, and the whiskers extend from the limit of the box to the largest or smallest value but no further than $1.5 \cdot IQR$ (inter quartile range).

Figure 4. Boxplots between average of organic carbon stock (OCstock, Kg C m⁻²) for the top 10 cm sediment and (A) EUSeaMap seabed substrata (based on EUNIS classification v2019), and (B) marine blue carbon vegetated habitats (broader definition, see Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023b)). Number of observations is indicated at the bottom of each box. The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 25-75 percentiles, and the whiskers extend from the limit of the box to the largest or smallest value but no further than 1.5*IQR (inter quartile range).

To further investigate the links between OC stocks and %OC (Figure 5), each data point was assigned a colour based on the EUNIS substratum associated with its geographic location. Additionally, the data points were differentiated by shape to represent the specific vegetated blue carbon habitat where the sample was collected. The vegetated habitats represented the majority of data points with the highest OC stocks with *Posidonia oceanica* being the primary contributor to the highest stocks. No clear patterns were found for cases where a data point had information about a non-biogenic EUNIS substrata and was vegetated according to in situ observations (Figure 5). For high OC contents, seagrass meadows exhibited the greatest variance of OC stock, and for low OC contents, saltmarshes had the highest variance (Figure 5B).

Figure 5. Relationship of (A) organic carbon (OC) stock to %OC and (B) OC stock to %OC on a log scale in the top 10 cm of the sediment. The data points are coloured according to the marine substrata EUNIS classification v2019 and shaped according to blue carbon habitat information.

Wave exposure model and environmental drivers

The geographical patterns of the average wave fetch index and wave exposure followed general expectations. Areas closer to the coastline had higher average wave fetch, while locations sheltered by islands and those further offshore had lower values. In this analysis it was clear that inlets and fjords had much lower values, reflecting their more sheltered locations, often close to more exposed shorelines. Additionally, locations further offshore and with deeper water had lower values. The highest values were obtained at locations on straight open coastlines which were open to uninterrupted exposure (Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 5. Examples of patterns in wave exposure and organic carbon content of sediments. Clockwise from top left: Svalbard, Lofoten region of Norway, west Scotland, Denmark and Sweden, and northwest France.

Figure 6. Map showing the spatial patterns in wave fetch and organic carbon (in %) in European seas. The colour scale for wave fetch is the same as in Figure 5.

The average relative contribution (in %) of each environmental predictor variable derived from the XGBoost analysis. Of the ten predictor variables for the sediment OC levels in coastal areas (< 5 km from the coastline) coastal wave exposure was clearly the most important (24%), followed by maximum temperature (20%), distance from shore (16%), water depth (9%) available radiation (8%) and nitrate (7%; Figure 7, Figure 8). The remaining environmental predictors described less than 5% of the variation of sediment OC levels within European seas (Figure 7, Figure 8).

Figure 7. Relative importance (in %) of environmental predictors in describing the organic carbon (OC) levels within European seas. Coastal exposure refers to wave exposure, and bathymetry refers to water depth. Dotted line indicates relative importance of environmental predictors at 5%, reflecting that variables below this threshold have minor importance.

Partial dependence plots show the individual effects of each environmental predictor variable on %OC we constructed partial dependence plots (Figure 8). For the main environmental predictor variables (coastal wave exposure, maximum temperature, distance from shore and water depth) we found clear differences in how OC responded to changes in these variables (Figure 8). The %OC decreased approximately linearly with increasing wave exposure and increasing maximum temperature (Figure 8). Carbon content decreased with distance from shore (Fig. 8). Increasing water depth had a dramatic negative effect on the sediment %OC, with the initial increase from shallower water to about 150-200 m depth having the largest impacts, while at water depths than approximately 500 m only minor effects were found (Figure 8).

Pearson's correlations show that some of the environmental predictor variables correlate with each other, such as water depth, nitrate and phosphate, as nitrate and phosphate concentrations increase with depth (Figure 9). Therefore, it is important to use expert judgement before potential “cause and effect relationships” are proposed.

The relationship between the logarithm of observed and model predicted sediment organic carbon (%OC) observations showed that our model explained 58% of the deviance (Figure 10).

Figure 8. Partial plots depicting the individual effect of each variable on the response variable (%OC). The relative contribution of the variables are in parenthesis. Coastal exposure refers to wave exposure.

Figure 9. Matrix of the Pearson's correlation (r) between all pairs of predictor variables, 0 (indicates no linear relationship) to 1 (indicates a perfect positive linear relationship) and direction (+/-) of the relationship between the two variables.

Figure 10. Relationship between the logarithm (Log-Log) of observed and model-predicted organic carbon (as %OC; deviance explained: 0.583).

Discussion

The OC dataset and associated information are based on in situ observations and direct measures done by data contributors (see Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023b)). These data are precise data points, while both EUSeaMap seabed substrata and EUNIS habitats (1:50k, see Vasquez et al. 2023)) as well as predictors variables (5 km, see Deliverable 2.1, (Assis et al. 2023b)) are produced at a coarser scale (approx. 5km). Such a difference is relevant when comparing and interpreting the scale at which OC levels vary. Any other major sources of uncertainty in the EUSeaMap information and predictor variables should be also considered in the interpretation of the results.

The capacity of marine sediments to trap and store OC vary widely both temporally and spatially, depending on a wide range of geomorphological, physical, chemical, and biological conditions. Due to this variability, it is challenging to determine OC inventories at a European Sea scale and the factors controlling these carbon stocks. Previous studies have determined that coastal and shelf sediments globally are hot spots of OC burial, with river deltas ($\approx 114 \text{ Tg C y}^{-1}$) and non-deltaic shelf ($\approx 70 \text{ Tg C y}^{-1}$) regions having burial rates that are approximately 19 and 10 times higher than those in the open ocean ($\approx 6 \text{ Tg C y}^{-1}$; Burdige 2005). In our analysis we used sediment OC data compiled in Deliverable 4.1 (Graversen et al. 2023b) plus Deliverable 4.2 (Graversen et al. 2023a) and matched these with environmental data to identify potential drivers of sediment OC levels at a European Sea level.

The relationships we found between %OC and OC stocks indicated that in large datasets %OC can be used as a good proxy for the storage of OC in the sediment. The exponential relationship between DBD and %OC will in our future work be used to calculate DBD for the data points where only %OC is reported to be able to predict the carbon stocks for those sediments. It should be noted that the %OC levels and OC stocks represent variable timescales of accumulation, which cannot be disentangled in our analysis as information on OC accumulation rates are only available for very few sites. Hence, in the interpretation of results it is important to consider that a given OC stock could have accumulated over a decadal or a Century-Millennial time scale.

In regards to habitat and substratum categories, we identified the largest OC content in finely grained sediments under the categories fine, and sandy mud, or muddy sand (although high OC-levels were also occasionally associated with mixed, coarser sediments, probably as a result of the coarse spatial resolution of classes) (Fig. 3A). This is in line with previous findings and relate to the fact that inorganic particles (e.g. clay, silt, carbonates) with high surface area have greater capacity than coarser sediments to adsorb organic matter (Keil & Mayer 2014). Furthermore, minerals can influence sediment redox gradients and accessibility to oxygen, which together with adsorption of OC to inorganic particles can impact OC degradation.

Sediments of *Posidonia*, other seagrasses and saltmarshes also represented relatively high OC content (Fig. 3-5). The ability of *Posidonia* meadows to build reefs makes it particularly efficient in storing OC (Fourqurean et al. 2012) and is the reason why it is defined as a specific EUNIS substratum. The other (non-reef forming) European seagrass species typically grow over sandy, silty and muddy sediments and may affect their OC content. Together with *Posidonia* and saltmarshes they dominate the observations of high OC-stocks and high OC content (Fig. 5). The finding of high OC content of seagrass- and saltmarsh sediments is a common observation and is, indeed, the reason why these habitats are often referred to as blue carbon habitats (e.g. Duarte et al. 2005; Mcleod et al. 2011; Temmink et al. 2022). The capacity of these ecosystems for carbon storage is related to the wave attenuating effect of their canopies, which supports sedimentation of fine particles as well as the leaf-fall from their own production while their roots and rhizomes stabilize the sediments Duarte

et al. 2013; Vizzini et al. 2019). However, despite a large capacity, there is a large variability in OC-storage also of the vegetated habitats.

Regarding the environmental predictors, from our analysis it was clear that wave exposure, itself varying with depth and distance from the coast, could describe most of the variation in the sediment OC levels. This intuitively makes sense, as higher current speed and wave exposure hinders deposition, increases erosion, and could fuel degradation of sediment OC (Zhao et al. 2024). Therefore, areas with low wave exposure will naturally have higher OC content due to: (1) increased sedimentation rates allowing a larger fraction of OC to reach the sediment; (2) decreased resuspension and remobilization of the OC already deposited which also minimises physical reworking and oxygen exposure time (Aller 1998); (3) generally increased water stratification which can fuel seasonal hypoxia leading to slower sediment OC degradation (Lee 1992); and (4) lower advective exchange between sediment and the overlying water leading to slower biogeochemical processing of the sediment derived OC (Huettel et al. 2014).

Our analysis identified maximum temperature in the study area as one of the main predictors, with warmer conditions decreasing the sediment OC content. Previous studies have demonstrated how changing temperatures can impact OC storage both directly and indirectly. In deeper waters elevated temperatures decrease the delivery of OC to the sediment due to intensified stratification of surface waters (Polovina et al. 2008; Sarmiento et al. 2004). This stratification will reduce the nutrient supply into the surface leading to less OC production and vertical exchange of organic material (e.g. phytoplankton) downwards, thereby reducing the overall delivery of OC to sediments. In addition, changes in temperature also affect the composition and amounts of planktonic and benthic primary production which in turn could also affect the delivery to the sediment (Brown et al. 2004; Gillooly et al. 2001). Moreover the microbial degradation of OC is temperature dependent, with higher temperatures stimulating the degradation and release of more recalcitrant OC fractions (Lønborg et al. 2018; Lønborg et al. 2020). Changing temperatures also directly (e.g., via oxygen solubility) and indirectly (e.g., via changed respiration and ocean ventilation) influence the overall oxygen content (Robinson 2019). Oxygen availability has been suggested as a key factor regulating sediment OC degradation with anoxic conditions ($0 \mu\text{mol O}_2 \text{ l}^{-1}$) leading to slower and less efficient degradation than at fully saturated (“oxic” $> 60 \mu\text{mol O}_2 \text{ l}^{-1}$) conditions (Jessen et al. 2017), which is consistent with observed higher OC concentrations in low oxygen-containing marine sediments (e.g., Middelburg et al. 1993). Nonetheless, some studies have also suggested that OC degradation is similar under oxic and anoxic conditions (e.g., Lee 1992). Overall, our result suggests that elevated temperatures decrease the sediment OC content, which most likely is explained by all the above-mentioned processes.

Variations in sediment OC are thought to decrease generally with distance from shore and increasing water depth (i.e. from lagoon to abyssal marine zones (Burdige 2007a). However this can vary depending on local environmental conditions geomorphology, hydrodynamics, and human activities (e.g. land use and coastal development) (Burdige 2007a). This general decrease with distance from shore and water depth was also clear from our analysis, which is influenced by a combination of factors, mainly linked to proximity to terrestrial inputs, as well as decreases in primary production and sedimentation rates with distance to shore and increasing water depth. Generally, sediments closer to the shore receive a higher input of OC from terrestrial sources such as rivers (Burdige 2005). The variables used here explained just 58% of the % OC variation. Including variables such as distance from river mouths may improve this statistic. In addition, coastal waters have higher primary productivity, both planktonic and benthic, which is mainly fuelled by nutrient inputs from rivers and coastal upwelling (Lønborg et al. 2021) and enhances the amount of OC reaching the sediment. Additionally, in the open ocean, a smaller fraction of the OC produced in the sunlit surface

layers reaches the sediment, which is mainly due to more of the OC being degraded and the OC being dispersed before reaching the sediment (Buesseler et al. 2007). Furthermore, nearshore areas are also to a larger extent impacted by strong currents, waves and tides which will affect the transport and deposition of organic material.

Overall, it is important to remember that the sediment OC content in any study area will also vary depending on local conditions, such as the presence of bioturbating organisms, which are known to increase sediment oxygen uptake and permeability as well as reduce the organic content and accumulation of reduced products in sediment pore water (Kristensen et al. 2012; Volkenborn et al. 2007). As we could not account for all these variables in our analysis, our results are applicable only over larger spatial scales and might not be applicable in certain study areas with varying organism presence, and local-scale variability in e.g. hydrodynamics, climate, and geomorphology.

Conclusion

Our study identified wave exposure, maximum temperature, distance from shore and water depth as the main environmental predictors of sediment OC content, with highest OC content in sheltered, cool, shallow near-shore locations. High OC content was also related to finely grained sediment and the presence of seagrass meadows (in particular meadows of *Posidonia oceanica*) and saltmarshes. However, OC levels varied markedly within specific substratum and habitat, which limit the capacity for generalisations.

Next steps

Within the coming months and year we will:

- Use the information on this report to create a draft OC-storage scoring system and maps.
- Update the analyses when the database described in Deliverables D4.1 and D4.2 is finalised.
- Draft a manuscript describing the updated analysis in detail.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. EUSeaMap seabed substrata

Data sources

The seabed substratum layer used was obtained from EUSeaMap 2023, a broad-scale seabed habitat map for Europe created by EMODnet Seabed Habitats (Vasquez et al, 2023). The aim of EUSeaMap is to categorise Europe's seabed habitats by categorising and combining the most important physical variables that drive the distribution of benthic communities, and for which full-coverage data layers exist or can be created.

Apart from the final habitat type, EUSeaMap contains categorised 'habitat descriptors' such as substratum type, biological zone, oxygen regime and energy level. For the 'substrate type' habitat descriptor, EMODnet Seabed Habitats produced a layer that compiled data from multiple sources and differing levels of detail, stitched together and reclassified into a common classification scheme.

Predominantly, it is sourced from the 2023 EMODnet Geology seabed substratum data product (Kaskela et al, 2019), with some additional data added by EMODnet Seabed Habitats (see Vasquez et al, 2023 for more details).

Classification

The seabed substratum layer is classified according to the so-called "Folk 7" classification, plus biogenic substrata. Once combined with a 'biological zone' and other habitat descriptors, this allows the final habitat classification to be expressed in terms of at least level 3 of the pan-European EUNIS habitat classification system (EUNIS marine version v2022).

Folk 7

"Folk 7" is a shorthand name for a simplified version Folk (1954) classification that reduces the original 15 classes down to 6 and adds an additional class for "rock and boulders" (sometimes referred to as "rock and other hard substrata") (Figure A1). This classification is equivalent to the substratum classes used at level 3 and 4 of the EUNIS v2022 classification system.

The majority of the Folk 7 data came from the 2023 EMODnet Geology multi-scale seabed substratum layer (Kaskela et al, 2019), with some subsequent changes by EMODnet Seabed Habitats (see Vasquez et al, 2023 for more details).

FOLK, 16 classes	FOLK, 7 classes	FOLK, 5 classes
Rock & Boulders	Rock & Boulders	Rock & Boulders
Gravel - G	Coarse sediment	Coarse sediment (Gravel >= 80% or (Gravel >= 5% and Sand >= 90%))
sandy Gravel - sG		
gravelly Sand - gS		
muddy Gravel - mG	Mixed sediment	Mixed sediment (Mud 95-10%; Sand < 90%; Gravel >= 5%)
muddy sandy Gravel - msG		
gravelly Mud - gM		
gravelly muddy Sand - gmS		
(gravelly) Mud - (g)M	Mud (Mud >= 90%; Sand < 10%; Gravel < 5%)	Mud to muddy Sand (Mud 100-10%; Sand < 90%; Gravel < 5%)
Mud - M	sandy Mud (Mud 50-90%; Sand 10-50%; Gravel < 5%)	
(gravelly) sandy Mud - (g)sM		
sandy Mud - sM	muddy Sand (Mud 10-50%; Sand 50-90%; Gravel < 5%)	
(gravelly) muddy Sand - (g)mS		
muddy Sand - mS	Sand (Mud < 10%; Sand >= 90%; Gravel < 5%)	
(gravelly) Sand - (g)S		Sand
Sand		

Figure A1. The Folk sediment triangle and the hierarchy of Folk classification (15, 6 and 4 classes, plus an additional class “rock and boulders,” indicated by the arrow) used in the EMODnet Geology project. From Kaskela et al (2019). For this project, the Folk 7 classification has been used, in combination with biogenic substrata.

Biogenic substrates

EUSeaMap was originally intended as a physical habitat map only, constructed from physical input data layers. In the most recent update to the EUNIS habitat classification system (EUNIS, 2022), “biogenic habitat” was placed at the same level in the classification hierarchy as other substratum types, therefore, to be able to classify EUSeaMap to level 3 of the EUNIS classification it was necessary to include a class for biogenic habitat in the list of substratum types.

Biogenic habitat (or “biogenic substratum”) for this purpose includes substratum-modifying features of biological origin that:

- Cover and replace the underlying substratum as a structuring factor, so that the underlying substrate cannot always be detected,
- Can occur on different substratum types, so that the underlying substrate cannot be presumed, and
- Are detectable using acoustic survey techniques, so that they are typically mapped in the same way as other substrate types (Lillis et al, 2021).

The following biogenic substratum types were chosen to be compatible with the terms used in the EUNIS v2022 habitat classification system (Lillis et al, 2021):

- biogenic detritic bottoms
- bivalve reefs, which include:
 - dominated by valve snails
 - *Hiatella arctica* beds
 - *Limaria hians* beds
 - mussel beds
 - dominated by zebra mussel
 - *Modiolus modiolus* beds
 - *Mytilus edulis* beds
 - *Ostrea edulis* beds
 - cold water coral reefs, which include:
 - *Lophelia pertusa* reefs
 - *Solenosmilia variabilis* reefs
 - coralligenous platforms
 - facies with *Ficopomatus enigmaticus* of the euryhaline and/or eurythermal lagoon biocenosis
 - peat bottoms
 - *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, which include:
 - Dead mattes of *Posidonia oceanica*
 - live *Posidonia oceanica* meadows
 - *Posidonia oceanica* "Barrier-reef"
 - shell gravel
 - worm reefs, which include:
 - *Sabellaria alveolata* reefs
 - *Sabellaria spinulosa* reefs
 - *Serpula vermicularis* reefs

The more specific the biogenic substratum, the further down the EUNIS hierarchy it is possible to classify. It should be noted that the inclusion of data on biogenic substrata in the data layer is heavily influenced by survey effort and has many data gaps.

What about other biological habitats?

Note that biological habitats that *do not* cover and replace the underlying substratum as a structuring factor, such as *Zostera* beds, can be found under their associated sediment type in the EUNIS hierarchy. For example:

M: Marine benthic habitat

MB5: Infralittoral sand

MB52: Atlantic infralittoral sand

MB522: Seagrass beds on Atlantic infralittoral sand

MB5223: *Zostera marina/angustifolia* beds on Atlantic infralittoral clean or muddy sand

Contrast this with the position of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows within the biogenic habitat substratum type:

M: Marine benthic habitat

MB2: Infralittoral biogenic habitat

MB25: Mediterranean infralittoral biogenic habitat

MB252: Biocenosis of *Posidonia oceanica*

Biological habitats such as *Zostera* beds are not included in EUSeaMap because EUSeaMap's primary goal is to map EUNIS level 3 habitats. However, EMODnet Seabed Habitats has produced separate data compilations showing the current best available data compilation on the European distribution of the following important marine habitats:

- Seagrass cover
- Live hard coral cover
- Macroalgal canopy cover
- Coralligenous and other calcareous bioconcretions (Mediterranean only)

These are available to view and download from the [EMODnet Map Viewer](#).

Reference in Appendix

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